

Some Aspects of Krilium Adsorption by Clay Minerals and Their Derivatives

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Adsorption of krilium has been found to lie in the following order when pure clay minerals are used: montmorillonite (Kashmir bentonite) > vermiculite (Mysore) > attapulgite (Georgia) > biotite (Rajasthan) > kaolinite (Bihar) > pyrophyllite (Jhansi). The adsorption by hydrogen and calcium derivatives of the clays also follow the same order. Calcium derivatives have the maximum adsorptive capacity; the minerals come next and the hydrogen derivatives exhibit the least adsorptive capacity.

Adsorption studies with krilium in presence of clay minerals have been made by a number of workers. Mukherjee¹ reported a few observations on the adsorption of krilium by hydrogen and calcium derivatives of Kashmir bentonite. From the studies of the base-exchange capacity of the treated clays, he found the adsorption of krilium incomplete with calcium clay and less with hydrogen clay. Krilium is believed to be held by co-ordination with calcium or hydrogen ions. Adsorption of krilium reduces the exchange capacity of hydrogen clay and increases the hydrophilic character as shown by water intake, but does not affect it for an organic solvent as toluene. Beutelspacher² found the adsorptive capacity of krilium to be lowest for quartz, moderate for kaolinite, and highest for montmorillonite. Allison³ noted that the soil conditioner was apparently strongly adsorbed on clay surfaces, forming bridges between the adjacent soil particles. The rate and extent of adsorption of C¹⁴ labelled HPAN on kaolinite was determined by Mortensen⁴. He observed a steady-state adsorption within four hours by continuous mixing in presence of univalent exchange ions and obtained the Langmuir-type adsorption isotherms. The effect of exchange cation (chloride salts) in increasing the adsorption of HPAN was in the order: Th⁴⁺ > Ca²⁺ > Ba²⁺ > H⁺ > NH₄⁺ > K⁺ > Na⁺. Anions of sodium salts increased the adsorption in the order: F⁻ > OH⁻ > H₂PO₄⁻ > Cl⁻ > CH₃COO⁻ > NO₃⁻ > HPAN. Ikeda and Harada⁵ attributed the lowering of dispersion ratio to the addition of krilium. Kamo-shita *et al*⁶. observed that the addition of krilium protected the soil from being washed away; they also noted⁷ that the effect of soil conditioner to the minimum air permeability was positive in the Ca-treated soil and negative in the Na-treated ones; it had a tendency to make larger aggregates in the former and smaller in the latter. Dhawan *et al*⁸. also

1. *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1954, 2, 99.
2. *Z. pflanz. Düng. Bodenk.*, 1955, 69, 108.
3. *Soil Sci.*, 1957, 83, 391.
4. *Soil Sci. Soc. Amer. Proc.*, 1957, 21, 385.
5. *J. Sci. Soil Manure*, 1955, 25, 303.
6. *Ibid.*, 1955, 25, 209.
7. *Ibid.*, 1953, 24, 235.
8. *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, 1955, 24A, 415.

supported the observations of Ikeda and Harada⁵ that krilium decreased the dispersion of clay soils effectively at 0.05 to 0.1% concentration.

It is evident from the above brief resume of work that the adsorption studies with krilium have not been made with wide varieties of minerals, specially with those of Indian origin. In this communication the adsorption of krilium by the following minerals of Indian origin have been studied: montmorillonite (Kashmir bentonite), pyrophyllite (Jhansi), kaolinite (Bihar), biotite (Rajasthan), vermiculite (Mysore), attapulgitite (Georgia) and their hydrogen and calcium derivatives.

EXPERIMENTAL

The sample of krilium was obtained from Monsanto Chemical Company (U.S.A.). As reported by the suppliers, this substance is a hydrolysed polyacrylonitrile resin. It is light yellow in colour, appreciably soluble in water, and is noted to possess considerable binding effect and high moisture-retaining capacity. From the above properties, it has been suggested to be a substitute for soil humus.

Preparation of Derivatives.—An aqueous solution of *N*/25-HCl was prepared in CO₂-free water. The minerals (15 g. each) were taken in the reagent bottles. The acid solution (100 ml) was added to each of them and the bottles were allowed to stand for 3 days with occasional shaking at regular intervals. The supernatant liquid was decanted and the solid mass was washed with distilled water by decantation. The above operations were repeated for further two days; the final washing was done by using a Sharple's super-centrifuge at 15,000 r.p.m. till the filtrate was free of chloride ions. The solid mass was taken out and dried in an air-oven at 100°. The dried mass was finely powdered in a mortar and stored in a desiccator as a hydrogen derivative of the mineral. The calcium derivatives of the minerals were similarly prepared by using saturated aqueous solution of calcium chloride.

The krilium sample was dried at 80° for an hour and then kept in a desiccator. About 0.35% of this dried substance was dissolved in water. The exact concentration of krilium was measured on the basis of nitrogen content by the salicylic acid reduction method⁹. The sample of krilium was found to contain 6.2% nitrogen.

Adsorption Studies.—The mineral or the derivatives (1g.) was taken in each of four one-litre volumetric flasks and to them 300, 400, 500, and 600 ml of the krilium solution were added and the volume of each was made to the mark by distilled water. The flasks were occasionally shaken and kept overnight at 30°. pH of the supernatant liquid was measured by a Leeds and Northrup pH-meter, operated on 220 volts/50 cycles mains, with a glass calomel electrode system supplied with the instrument. The supernatant liquid (100 ml) from each of the volumetric flasks was taken in different Kjeldahl flasks and the unadsorbed nitrogen was estimated by the salicylic acid method⁹. The pH of the krilium solution, diluted to 1000 ml, was 4.25 in every case.

⁹, Treadwell and Hall, "Analytical Chemistry", 1947 p. 453.

TABLE I

Absorption of krilium.

Concentration (mg./litre.) Original.	*Krilium Final.	pH of adsorbed.	pH of mixture.	Final conc. adsorbed.	*Krilium adsorbed.	pH of mixture.	Final conc. adsorbed.	*Krilium adsorbed.	pH of mixture.
1. Montmorillonite (Kashmir bentonite).			H-montmorillonite (Kashmir bentonite).			Ca-montmorillonite (Kashmir bentonite).			
1048.44	809.40	179.04	4.45	942.52	105.92	4.33	759.04	288.80	4.55
1397.92	1175.92	222.00	4.35	1263.52	134.40	4.28	1027.52	370.40	4.47
1747.40	1462.40	285.00	4.30	1569.40	178.00	4.25	1274.40	473.00	4.40
2096.88	1710.48	386.40	4.28	1873.92	222.96	4.25	1402.96	633.92	4.37
2. Pyrophyllite (Jhansi).			H-pyrophyllite (Jhansi).			Ca-pyrophyllite (Jhansi).			
1048.44	960.24	88.20	4.45	987.44	61.00	4.42	895.80	152.64	4.55
1397.92	1260.48	137.44	4.38	1316.48	81.44	4.37	1176.12	221.80	4.50
1747.40	1534.92	192.48	4.35	1623.00	124.40	4.30	1442.68	304.72	4.47
2096.88	1807.92	288.96	4.30	1940.44	156.44	4.28	1636.00	460.88	4.40
3. Kaolinite (Bihar).			H-kaolinite (Bihar).			Ca-kaolinite (Bihar).			
1048.44	935.44	113.00	4.50	975.04	72.40	4.43	859.32	189.12	4.60
1397.92	1230.00	161.92	4.40	1303.84	94.08	4.37	1138.48	259.44	4.50
1747.40	1529.92	217.48	4.38	1610.80	136.60	4.33	1402.40	345.00	4.45
2096.88	1783.28	313.60	4.35	1927.76	169.12	4.30	1597.76	499.12	4.40
4. Biotite (Rajasthan).			H-biotite (Rajasthan).			Ca-biotite (Rajasthan).			
1048.44	918.60	129.84	4.50	968.24	80.20	4.42	834.28	214.16	4.60
1397.92	1225.52	172.40	4.42	1294.64	103.28	4.40	1113.68	284.24	4.50
1747.40	1511.92	235.48	4.38	1602.40	145.00	4.35	1377.40	370.00	4.48
2096.88	1766.80	330.08	4.35	1917.92	178.96	4.30	1572.72	524.16	4.43
5. Vermiculite (Mysore).			H-vermiculite (Mysore).			Ca-vermiculite (Mysore).			
1048.44	876.84	171.60	4.50	945.84	102.60	4.40	776.04	272.40	4.60
1397.92	1184.92	213.00	4.40	1288.80	129.12	4.33	1052.40	345.52	4.50
1747.40	1470.60	276.80	4.37	1574.00	172.80	4.30	1306.36	441.04	4.45
2096.88	1719.44	377.44	4.33	1879.76	217.12	4.25	1502.88	594.00	4.40
6. Attapulgit (Georgia).			H-attapulgit (Georgia).			Ca-attapulgit (Georgia).			
1048.44	801.40	157.04	4.55	955.84	92.60	4.40	797.08	251.96	4.65
1397.92	1197.60	200.32	4.45	1280.48	117.44	4.35	1077.28	320.64	4.55
1747.40	1485.52	261.88	4.40	1587.88	159.52	4.32	1337.00	410.40	4.45
2096.88	1737.84	359.04	4.35	1900.40	196.48	4.30	1536.48	560.40	4.40

*By 1g. clay in mg.

DISCUSSION

The data in Table I show that the adsorptive capacity of the various minerals lie in the order: montmorillonite > vermiculite > attapulgit > biotite > kaolinite > pyrophyllite. The adsorptive capacity of the derivatives also follows the same order.

The calcium derivatives have maximum adsorptive capacity, the minerals themselves come next, and hydrogen derivatives have the least adsorptive capacity. This is in conformity with the observations made by Mukherjee¹.

TABLE II

Absorption of krypton by various clay minerals (1g. each) and their derivatives.

*Original conc.	Bentonite (Kashmir).	Vermiculite (Mysore).	Attapulgit (Georgia).	Biotite (Rajasthan).	Kaolinite (Bihar).	Pyrophyllite (Jhansi).
A. Original minerals.						
1048.44	179.04	171.60	157.04	129.84	113.00	88.20
1397.92	222.00	213.00	200.32	172.40	161.92	137.44
1747.40	285.00	276.80	261.88	235.48	217.48	192.48
2096.88	386.40	377.44	359.04	330.08	313.60	288.96
B. H-derivatives.						
1048.44	105.92	102.60	92.60	80.20	72.40	61.00
1397.92	134.40	129.12	117.44	103.28	94.08	81.44
1747.40	178.00	172.80	159.52	145.00	136.60	124.40
2096.88	222.96	217.12	196.48	178.96	169.12	156.44
C. Ca-derivatives.						
1048.44	288.80	272.40	251.36	214.16	189.12	152.64
1397.92	370.40	345.52	320.64	284.24	259.44	221.80
1747.40	473.00	441.04	410.40	370.00	345.00	304.72
2096.88	633.92	594.00	560.40	524.16	499.12	480.88

TABLE III

Percentage adsorption of krypton by clay minerals and their derivatives.

*Original conc.	Bentonite (Kashmir).	Vermiculite (Mysore).	Attapulgit (Georgia).	Biotite (Rajasthan).	Kaolinite (Bihar).	Pyrophyllite (Jhansi).
A. Original minerals.						
1048.44	17.0	16.4	15.0	12.4	10.8	8.4
1397.92	15.9	15.2	14.3	12.3	11.6	9.8
1747.40	16.5	15.8	15.0	13.6	12.4	11.0
2096.88	18.4	18.0	17.1	15.7	15.0	13.6
B. H-derivatives.						
1048.44	10.0	9.8	8.9	7.6	6.9	5.8
1397.92	9.6	9.2	8.5	7.4	6.7	5.8
1747.40	10.2	9.9	9.2	8.3	7.9	7.1
2096.88	10.7	10.4	9.4	8.5	8.0	7.4
C. Ca-derivatives.						
1048.44	27.6	26.0	24.0	20.4	18.0	14.7
1397.92	26.5	24.8	23.0	20.3	18.5	15.9
1747.40	27.1	25.2	23.5	21.2	19.7	16.6
2096.88	30.2	28.3	26.7	25.0	23.8	22.0

*Concentration expressed in mg./litre.

The adsorption values do not obey the Freundlich and the Langmuir equations (graphs not shown to economise space). This leads to the conclusion that the association of krilium with the clay minerals is not of an adsorptive nature, but it involves other factors, like chemical process, specially for higher concentrations of krilium or other processes like change in the size of adsorbent particles, chemical interaction or multilayer adsorption.

The observations on the change in pH offer interest. It may be noted that the initial pH of the krilium solution is 4.25 in every case and after the attainment of equilibrium, alkali is liberated, resulting in an increase of pH. This increase is found to be most significant with the calcium derivatives and least with the hydrogen derivatives, whereas the change with the minerals is intermediate between the two. Incidentally, this is in the same order as the adsorptive capacities of the different derivatives.

In the case of adsorption by hydrogen clays (Table III, B), the percentage adsorption of krilium does not depend on the concentration of krilium taken and is more or less constant. In the case of the clay minerals or the calcium derivatives, there is a significant rise in the percentage adsorption with increase in the concentration of krilium added (Table III).

The mechanism of the association of krilium with the minerals is complicated. It, however, appears that the CN groups of the polyacrylonitrile contain lone pair of valency electrons, which are available for forming co-ordinate bonds. These lead to the formation of complexes with the metals in the clay minerals. Evidently, hydrogen is a poor acceptor than other elements and hence the association of krilium with hydrogen clays are less in comparison with calcium clay or the clay itself.

This investigation therefore leads to the conclusion that the useful effect of krilium is likely to be more marked for Ca-derivatives of the minerals, i.e., in the presence of calcium salts, the effect of krilium is expected to be more beneficial as a soil conditioner.

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